

A Taxonomy of Incident Management in Proprietary Software Ecosystems

You are being invited to participate in a part of study conducted by researchers:
<<omitted due to privacy reasons>>

This study aims to explore the governance of incident management in proprietary software ecosystems (PSECO). These ecosystems are characterized by collaboration between multiple stakeholders on a common technology platform, protected by intellectual property and confidentiality agreements. The study will be conducted in close collaboration with professionals from a large international organization, employing the Rapid Review (RR) method.

The lack of an optimized incident management process can prevent developers from ensuring reliability and protecting services against failures. This gap can challenge the organization management team in defining governance strategies to evaluate decisions related to the PSECO technology platform. Our study seeks to fill this gap by exploring governance strategies for incident management.

Personal identification data will not be mentioned in the research report, which will preserve the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants. Your contribution is extremely important for this research. We thank you for your kind collaboration!

Free and Informed Consent Form

PARTICIPANTS

The target audience for the research is researchers and practitioners from academia and industry with experience in software ecosystems, IT governance, IT service management, and incident management.

PROCEDURE

The study will be conducted in close collaboration with seven practitioners and three researchers, following the rapid review method across three main phases: planning, execution, and reporting. During the planning phase, practitioners will contribute to defining the research questions and aligning the study with practical needs. In the execution phase, practitioners will help refine the search strategy, inclusion/exclusion criteria, and evaluation of selected studies, actively participating in meetings to connect findings with industry demands. In the reporting phase, practitioners will assist in reviewing the results and validating the taxonomy elements, ensuring its practical relevance for addressing real challenges in PSECO.

By agreeing to participate in this research, you agree to the terms described below.

INVOLVEMENT IN THE RESEARCH

By participating in this study, I allow the researchers to gather information about my profile and my knowledge of software ecosystems, IT governance, IT service management, and incident management to use excerpts from my answers during the evaluation of the taxonomy. I am aware that I can refuse to participate or refuse to continue participating at any stage of the research without any prejudice.

CONFIDENTIALITY

I am aware that the data obtained through this study will be kept confidential. The results will later be presented in aggregate form so that a participant is not associated with specific data, guaranteeing their anonymity during the dissemination of the results.

I am aware that the data collected in this research will be used for academic purposes, and the results may be published in scientific media such as congresses and journals. Therefore, I undertake not to communicate my results until the study has been completed and to keep the techniques and documents presented as part of the study confidential.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORT

I understand that my participation in this rapid review is completely voluntary and that refusing to participate will not involve any penalty or loss of benefits. I also understand that, if I choose to participate, I will have to collaborate during the taxonomy evaluation and that, if I do not feel comfortable or feel tired, I can withdraw from the study, without any prejudice.

BENEFITS AND EXPENSES

There are no personal expenses or financial compensation for participating in this study, as the research does not suggest burdens to the participants.

I understand that once the taxonomy has been completed, the data provided will be studied to analyze the incident management governance in proprietary software ecosystems. Finally, I declare that I participate of my own free will with the sole intention of contributing to the purpose of this study.

If you have any questions, please write to <<*omitted due to privacy reasons*>>